

Comment on “Symmetry analysis and invariant solutions of the multipoint infinite systems describing turbulence”

A comment to M. Oberlack and M. Waclawczyk to appeal for better research

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Abstract

Although knowing better due to numerous comments and discussions in the past two years, M. Oberlack and M. Waclawczyk continue to publish incorrect research results. This note helps to see why in a very illustrative form.

1. The necessity for another Comment

The recent publication [J. Phys. Conf. Ser. 760, 012038 \(2016\)](#) by Waclawczyk & Oberlack gives conclusions which are not justified by the results. In fact, it faces the following specific problems: (i) The investigation on invariant solutions in turbulent channel flow is built on an incorrect statement, upon which then (ii) a universal statistical scaling law of the mean velocity profile for *low* Reynolds numbers is derived that when matched to DNS data it, firstly, cannot predict the complex *non*-universal flow behavior beyond the viscous sublayer and, secondly, that it can be replaced by a simpler scaling law that would achieve the same poor prediction quality. (iii) A derived correlation function for homogenous isotropic turbulence (HIT) turns out to be zero by closer inspection. Hence, particularly this latter issue, where Waclawczyk & Oberlack claim to have analytically obtained the decay law of turbulent kinetic energy in freely decaying HIT, cannot be confirmed.

2. The incorrect statement based on the “symmetry modification”

On *p. 3* in Waclawczyk & Oberlack (2016) it is stated that the general symmetries *Eqs. (4)-(6)* of the unbounded Lundgren-Monin-Novikov (LMN) equations for the probability density functions (PDFs) induces the following invariant transformation for the mean velocity profile

$$x_2^* = e^{k_2} x_2, \quad \langle U \rangle^* = e^{a_s - k_2} \langle U \rangle + C_1(1 - x_2^2/H^2), \quad (2.1)$$

of the statistical equations for turbulent channel flow, when only “modifying” the unbounded symmetries *Eqs. (4)-(6)*, “due to the presence of boundaries” [*p. 3*], accordingly. But as already clearly shown in Frewer *et al.* (2014),[†] this “modified combined symmetry” does not constitute a symmetry of the LMN equations, neither for the general unbounded nor for the particular

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[†]The abridged version (Frewer *et al.*, 2015a) was published as a Comment in Phys. Rev. E — in this respect, please also see our reactions (Frewer *et al.*, 2015b,c) to a Reply to this Comment.

bounded case of turbulent channel flow.[†] The incorporated boundaries for a channel, symbolized in (2.1) by the channel half-height parameter H , do not allow for such a “modified symmetry” in the LMN equations. In other words, transformation (2.1) does not qualify as a symmetry transformation to generate invariant *solutions* as the one derived in Eq. (9), which by the way is not even the correct invariant function to (2.1) due to a technical mistake in their derivation (see the next section for details). If possible, only a correct invariant *function*

$$\langle U \rangle = F(x_2; k_2, a_s, C_1; H) \xleftrightarrow{(2.1)} \langle U \rangle^* = F(x_2^*; k_2, a_s, C_1; H), \quad (2.2)$$

may be derived from the variable transformation (2.1), but which, however, will turn out to be a highly non-trivial task because (2.1) does not constitute a Lie-group transformation, thus facing the problem that it cannot be globally characterized by an infinitesimal representation. But once derived,[‡] this function (2.2) cannot be classified as an invariant *solution* of the statistical equations, simply because its transformation (2.1) is not induced by a symmetry of its underlying statistical LMN equations — in fact, relation (2.2) would be nothing more than just a function staying invariant under the arbitrarily chosen variable transformation (2.1), showing no relation to the invariance properties of the underlying statistical equations.

Besides the fact that this “modified PDF symmetry” [Eq. (54) in Waclawczyk *et al.* (2014)] is not admitted as a symmetry by the LMN equations for turbulent channel flow, the reader should further note that the two new statistical symmetries Eqs. (5) & (6) themselves additionally not only violate the classical principle of causality (Frewer *et al.*, 2016a), but that they also must get broken in order to be consistent with *all* physical constraints naturally arising in the statistical LMN description of turbulence (Frewer *et al.*, 2014, 2015a).

3. The incorrect derivation of an “invariant function”

The variable transformation (2.1) is *not* a Lie-group transformation as wrongly assumed on p. 3 in Waclawczyk & Oberlack (2016). Hence, their conclusion to Eq. (7) is wrong, since only a Lie-group transformation can be fully characterized by infinitesimal generators. That (2.1) does not form a Lie-group can be readily seen by performing two consecutive transformations^{‡‡}

$$\left. \begin{aligned} x_2^{**} &= e^{k_2^*} x_2^* = e^{k_2^* + k_2} x_2 = e^{\phi_1} x_2, \\ \langle U \rangle^{**} &= e^{a_s^* - k_2^*} \langle U \rangle^* + C_1^* (1 - x_2^{*2} / H^2) \\ &= e^{a_s^* + a_s - (k_2^* + k_2)} \langle U \rangle + e^{a_2^* - k_2^*} C_1 (1 - x_2^2 / H^2) + C_1^* (1 - e^{2k_2} x_2^2 / H^2) \\ &\neq e^{\phi_2 - \phi_1} \langle U \rangle + \phi_3 (1 - x_2^2 / H^2), \text{ where } \phi_i = \phi_i(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^*, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}), \text{ with } \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = (k_2, a_s, C_1), \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (3.1)$$

which shows that the composition axiom of a Lie-group for three parameters is violated, since no unique composition law $\boldsymbol{\phi} = (\phi_1, \phi_2, \phi_3)$ can be constructed; even if we would assume only a 1D-subgroup $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = (k_2, a_s, C_1) = \varepsilon \cdot (k_2', a_s', C_1')$ with a single group parameter ε , for which $\phi_1/k_2' = \phi_2/a_s' = \phi_3/C_1' =: \phi(\varepsilon^*, \varepsilon)$, transformation (3.1) still does *not* form a Lie-group. This can also be seen by the fact that the infinitesimal generators of Eq. (7) in Waclawczyk & Oberlack (2016) do not correspond to the finite transformation (2.1) proposed on p. 3. When applying Lie’s first theorem, for example for 1D-groups, to the infinitesimals of Eq. (7)

[†]The key part of this incorrectly claimed “symmetry” is derived as the result Eq. (54) in Waclawczyk *et al.* (2014), by “modifying” the new statistical PDF translation symmetry denoted here as Eq. (6).

[‡]For non-Lie-group transformations the condition for invariance (2.2) can mostly be solved, if possible, only locally in some point, but in general not globally as for Lie-group transformations.

^{‡‡}Note that three parameters are assumed as group parameters: k_2 , a_s and C_1 . The latter one stems from the derivation of Eq. (55) in Waclawczyk *et al.* (2014), which again has its origin in the new (unphysical) statistical translation symmetry Eq. (43).

correctly, one obtains, instead of (2.1), the corresponding (1D) Lie-group transformation

$$x_2^* = e^{k_2} x_2, \quad \langle U \rangle^* = e^{a_s - k_2} \langle U \rangle + C_1 \left(\frac{e^{a_s - k_2} - 1}{a_s - k_2} + \frac{e^{a_s - k_2} - e^{2k_2}}{3k_2 - a_s} \frac{x_2^2}{H^2} \right), \quad (3.2)$$

with the single group parameter ε rendered as $(k_2, a_s, C_1) = \varepsilon \cdot (k'_2, a'_s, C'_1)$, which then in the considered limit $a_s \rightarrow k_2$

$$x_2^* = e^{k_2} x_2, \quad \langle U \rangle^* = \langle U \rangle + \frac{C_1}{2k_2} (1 - e^{2k_2}) \frac{x_2^2}{H^2} + C_1, \quad (3.3)$$

also is the correct transformation that leaves the function of Eq. (9) in Waćlawczyk & Oberlack (2016) invariant, and *not* transformation (2.1) as wrongly claimed therein.[†] But with (3.3), although correct, we now face another serious problem: Transformation (3.3) does not correspond to the induced LMN transformation when combining the LMN symmetries Eqs. (4) & (5) with the “modified” translation symmetry of Eq. (6), which itself is explicitly given by Eq. (54) in Waćlawczyk *et al.* (2014). The proof is given in Appendix A. Hence, no matter how one tries to turn or to correct it, the proposed invariant function Eq. (9) is inconsistent.[‡]

4. Matching the “scaling law” to DNS

The intention of the (inconsistently) derived scaling law Eq. (69) in Waćlawczyk *et al.* (2014), and now newly proposed again in Waćlawczyk & Oberlack (2016) as Eq. (10)

$$\langle U \rangle = \gamma u_\tau \frac{1}{\kappa} \ln(x_2) + (1 - \gamma) U_L \left(1 - \frac{x_2^2}{H^2} \right) + C', \quad (4.1)$$

is to statistically predict the intermittent laminar-turbulent flow behavior of a plane channel flow for low Reynolds numbers $Re_\tau > Re_\tau^{cr}$, beyond the critical value Re_τ^{cr} where laminar solutions are realizable. The scaling (4.1) represents a simple blending between the laminar solution and the universal log-law of turbulent channel flow with the blending factor Eq. (13)

$$\gamma = \frac{1}{1 + (\kappa Re)^{-1}}, \quad \text{where } Re = Re_\tau = u_\tau H / \nu. \quad (4.2)$$

The value $\gamma = 1$ should correspond to the fully developed turbulent log-law profile for high $Re_\tau \rightarrow \infty$ with the universal von-Kármán constant κ , and $\gamma = 0$ to the fully developed laminar profile for low $Re_\tau \rightarrow 0$. Although the previous theoretical investigation clearly demonstrated that the scaling (4.1) shows no relation to the invariant properties of the underlying statistical equations, we nevertheless want to treat it as a simple model function in order to investigate its predictive ability to forecast the complex, non-universal flow behavior in a turbulent channel flow “with Re close to its critical value where the laminar-turbulent transition takes place” (Waćlawczyk & Oberlack, 2016, p. 3).

However, before (4.1) can be compared to DNS data, it first needs to be correctly adjusted. As it stands, the scaling shows an inconsistency in the wall-normal coordinate x_2 . The first part in (4.1), i.e. the universal log-part, is defined as an increasing function from the wall ($x_2 = 0$) to the channel center ($x_2 = H$), while the second, laminar part is defined in a coordinate system where the channel center is located oppositely at $x_2 = 0$ and the wall at $x_2 = H$. Hence, the laminar part in (4.1) has to be reformulated into the coordinate system

[†]It can be readily verified that the LMN induced transformation (2.1), as proposed on p. 3 in Waćlawczyk & Oberlack (2016), does not leave the function Eq. (9) invariant, that is, relation Eq. (9) is not an invariant function of transformation (2.1) as incorrectly and misleadingly claimed by Oberlack *et al.*

[‡]To note is that this twofold error, namely that the function Eq. (9) is not invariant under transformation (2.1) and that then its correct transformation (3.3) does not correspond to the “modified” combined LMN symmetries Eqs. (4)-(6), has not been detected by us before in our comments (Frewer *et al.*, 2014, 2015a,b,c), and thus marks a further crucial error in the already numerous list of errors mentioned therein.

Figure 1: *Left plot:* Mean velocity profile $\langle U \rangle^+$ of fully developed turbulent channel flow for different low Reynolds numbers in the range $Re_\tau \sim 80 - 650$ (solid lines from left to right). The numerical simulation for the lowest case $Re_\tau \sim 80$ was performed with the code of Lundbladh *et al.* (1992), while the remaining four cases $Re_\tau \sim 110, 150, 300, 650$ have been taken from the DNS database of Iwamoto *et al.* (2002*a,b*). The dotted lines show the two extreme cases: The curved line the laminar solution for the low Reynolds number case of $Re_\tau \sim 80$, and the straight line the universal log-law $\langle U \rangle^+ = (1/\kappa) \cdot \ln(x_2^+) + B$ for the high Reynolds number case of $Re_\tau \sim 5200$, taken from Lee & Moser (2015) with the von-Kármán constant $\kappa = 0.384$ and $B = 4.27$.

Right plot: Best fit (dashed line) of the proposed scaling law (4.4) to the DNS data (solid line) for the low Reynolds number case $Re_\tau \sim 150$ as also shown on the left in the valid range $20 < x_2^+ < Re_\tau$, i.e., from beyond the viscous layer to the center of the channel. The fitting parameter is $\mathcal{C}^+ = 4.41$, with the universal von-Kármán constant chosen as $\kappa = 0.384$ (Lee & Moser, 2015).

of the log-law in order to obtain a correct and consistent scaling relation, which thus then reads

$$\langle U \rangle = \gamma u_\tau \frac{1}{\kappa} \ln(x_2) + (1 - \gamma) U_L \frac{x_2}{H} \left(2 - \frac{x_2}{H} \right) + \mathcal{C}'. \quad (4.3)$$

The left panel in Figure 1 shows the DNS data of the mean velocity profile (normalized on u_τ) of fully developed turbulent channel flow for different low Reynolds numbers. The profile shows a complex, non-universal behavior beyond the viscous sublayer from $x_2^+ > 10$ onwards up to the center of the channel at $x_2^+ = Re_\tau$. For increasing Reynolds numbers the complex structure in this region flattens out to the universal log-layer, valid in an overlap region between the inner (viscous sublayer) and the outer layer (proximate to channel center) of the flow.

The right panel in Figure 1 shows the best fit of the non-dimensionalized scaling law (4.3) in ‘+’-units, i.e. relative to the near wall length scale ν/u_τ and the velocity scale u_τ

$$\langle U \rangle^+ = \frac{\gamma}{\kappa} \ln(x_2^+) + (1 - \gamma) \frac{x_2^+}{2} \left(2 - \frac{x_2^+}{Re_\tau} \right) + \mathcal{C}^+, \quad (4.4)$$

to the DNS data of $Re_\tau \sim 150$ in the relevant region $20 < x_2^+ < Re_\tau$ where (4.4) is claimed to be valid. The universal von-Kármán constant has been chosen as $\kappa = 0.384$, a value recently determined by Lee & Moser (2015), thus giving, according to (4.2), a blending factor of $\gamma \sim 0.98$, the same value as evaluated in Waćlawczyk & Oberlack (2016) for this Reynolds number case. Therein it is claimed that $\gamma \sim 0.98$ is a “reasonable result” [p. 4] which, however, is not plausible when looking at the functional structure of the fit in Figure 1 (right panel), and in more detail in Figure 2 (left panel). In the relevant region $20 < x_2^+ < Re_\tau$, the value of γ is way too high to allow for some “interesting” contribution of the laminar part of (4.4). Over the whole region the straight line of the log-law dominates, but due to its universal scaling behavior only for very high Reynolds numbers between the inner and outer layer of the flow, it is, obviously, not the appropriate and correct law to predict the complex and *non*-universal behavior in that region for low Reynolds numbers.

Figure 2: *Left plot:* Comparing the best-fit (dashed lines) of the proposed scaling law (4.4) to the DNS data (solid lines) of Figure 1 between the two low Reynolds number cases $Re_\tau \sim 80$ and $Re_\tau \sim 150$ (from top to bottom) in the valid range $20 < x_2^+ < Re_\tau$, i.e., from beyond the viscous layer to the center of the channel. The fitting parameters are $C^+ = 5.29$ and $C^+ = 4.41$ for the cases $Re_\tau \sim 80$ and $Re_\tau \sim 150$, respectively. The universal von-Kármán constant was again chosen as $\kappa = 0.384$ (Lee & Moser, 2015).

Right plot: Comparing the best-fit of the alternatively proposed one-parametric scaling law (4.5) to the one of (4.4) fitted on the left of this figure. The fitting parameters are $\lambda = 4.18$ and $\lambda = 4.49$ for the cases $Re_\tau \sim 80$ and $Re_\tau \sim 150$, respectively. As before, κ was fixed again to $\kappa = 0.384$.

Including also the very low Reynolds case of $Re_\tau \sim 80$ as a comparison to the $Re_\tau \sim 150$ case, Figure 2 (left panel) clearly demonstrates that it is not reasonable to fit the DNS data in that region by a straight line. To use the straight line (here in the log-linear frame) as a modelling function can unfortunately always be misused to ‘fit’ any data. For example, instead of (4.4) one can alternatively also propose the one-parametric scaling function

$$\langle U \rangle^+ = \frac{1}{\alpha} \ln(x_2^+) + \lambda, \quad \text{with } \alpha = \frac{\kappa}{1 + 2 \cdot \left(\frac{\pi^2}{\kappa Re_\tau} \right)^2} \stackrel{Re_\tau \rightarrow \infty}{=} \kappa, \quad (4.5)$$

showing not only the same fitting quality in the free (translation) parameter λ as (4.4) in C^+ , but also the same high Reynolds number property as (4.4) in tending to the von-Kármán log-law in the limit $Re_\tau \rightarrow \infty$.

Hence, if (4.4) is claimed to be a “reasonable” scaling function for low Reynolds number turbulent flow as in Waclawczyk *et al.* (2014) and Waclawczyk & Oberlack (2016), so is (4.5). But of course such a claim cannot be taken serious, neither for (4.5) nor for (4.4). Important (non-universal) structures in the mean flow cannot be captured with such oversimplified *ad hoc* scaling proposals. The intermittent flow behavior in a channel for low Reynolds numbers is more complex than just to blend between a fully turbulent and a fully laminar profile. For a definitely more promising ansatz to model a flow close to its critical value where the laminar-turbulent transition takes place, see e.g. the excellent investigation by Barkley (2016).

5. The zero correlation function

For homogeneous isotropic turbulence (HIT), the following analytical solution to the Hopf equations *Eqs. (14) & (15)* in Waclawczyk & Oberlack (2016) is proposed (see *p. 7*)

$$\Phi = 1 + C_1 + C_2 + \dots, \quad (5.1)$$

with $C_1 = 0$ and C_2 given by Eqs. (33)

$$C_2 = \int \frac{1}{t_1} F_{ij}(a_1, \dots, a_5) y_i(\mathbf{x}_{(1)}, t_1) y_j(\mathbf{x}_{(2)}, t_2) d^3 \mathbf{x}_{(1)} dt_1 d^3 \mathbf{x}_{(2)} dt_2, \quad (5.2)$$

where the a_i are given as [†]

$$a_1 = \frac{t_1}{t_2}, \quad a_2 = \frac{t_1 - t_2}{t_1}, \quad a_{2+k} = \frac{(x_{(1)k} - x_{(2)k})^2}{t_1 - t_2}, \quad k = 1, 2, 3. \quad (5.3)$$

Higher order terms C_n ($n > 2$) in the expansion (5.1) can be calculated from Eq. (28) in Waławczyk & Oberlack (2016) by “an analogous procedure, considering larger number of points $\mathbf{x}_{(1)}$, $\mathbf{x}_{(2)}$, $\mathbf{x}_{(3)}$, $\mathbf{x}_{(4)}$ etc. and larger number of times” [p. 7]. However, what is not mentioned in Waławczyk & Oberlack (2016) and which turns out to be crucial in the proof given below, is that this “analogous procedure” will lead to a power expansion in the time coordinate, say t_1 , where its next higher order term, when prolonging the procedure in Eq. (31) accordingly, will read

$$C_3 = \int \frac{1}{t_1^{3/2}} F_{ijk}(a_1, \dots, a_{n \geq 6}) y_i(\mathbf{x}_{(1)}, t_1) y_j(\mathbf{x}_{(2)}, t_2) y_k(\mathbf{x}_{(3)}, t_3) d^3 \mathbf{x}_{(1)} dt_1 d^3 \mathbf{x}_{(2)} dt_2 d^3 \mathbf{x}_{(3)} dt_3, \quad (5.4)$$

where the list of invariants a_i (5.3)[†] can be, for example, extended to

$$\left. \begin{aligned} a_6 &= \frac{t_1}{t_3}, & a_7 &= \frac{t_1 - t_3}{t_1}, & a_8 &= \frac{(t_1 + t_2 + t_3)^2}{(t_1 - t_2)^2 + (t_2 - t_3)^2 + (t_1 - t_3)^2}, \\ a_9 &= \frac{t_1 t_2 t_3}{(t_1 + t_2 + t_3)^3}, & a_{10+k} &= \frac{(x_{(1)k} - x_{(3)k})^2}{t_1 + t_3}, \quad k = 1, 2, 3. \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (5.5)$$

In the most general case, solution (5.1) would represent a power expansion in t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n , when applying the “analogous procedure” to all time points separately — see also Waławczyk & Oberlack (2013), where this formal procedure (for equal-time correlations in Fourier space) is presented in more detail.

Now, in order to analytically predict the HIT decay law of kinetic energy from the second functional derivative of Φ (5.1) as given in Eq. (34)[‡]

$$i^2 \langle U_i(\mathbf{x}_{(1)}, t_1) U_j(\mathbf{x}_{(2)}, t_2) \rangle := \frac{\delta^2 \Phi}{\delta y_i(\mathbf{x}_{(1)}, t_1) \delta y_j(\mathbf{x}_{(2)}, t_2)} \Big|_{\mathbf{y}=\mathbf{0}} = \frac{1}{t_1} F_{ij} + \frac{1}{t_2} F_{ji}, \quad (5.6)$$

the particular solution $F_{ij} = \text{const.}$ in Waławczyk & Oberlack (2016) is considered by making the choice $\mathbf{x}_{(1)} = \mathbf{x}_{(2)}$ and $t_1 = t_2$.^{‡‡} But this particular (1-point) choice in the solution (5.1)

$$\Phi = 1 + C_1 + C_2 + \dots = 1 + F_{ij} \cdot \int \frac{1}{t_1} y_i(\mathbf{x}_{(1)}, t_1) y_j(\mathbf{x}_{(2)}, t_2) d^3 \mathbf{x}_{(1)} dt_1 d^3 \mathbf{x}_{(2)} dt_2 + \mathcal{O}(1/t_1^{3/2}), \quad (5.7)$$

[†]As a result of solution (5.6), which is characterized by $\langle U_i(\mathbf{x}_{(1)}, t_1) U_j(\mathbf{x}_{(2)}, t_2) \rangle = \langle U_j(\mathbf{x}_{(2)}, t_2) U_i(\mathbf{x}_{(1)}, t_1) \rangle$, namely to comply with the self-evident re-labeling invariance between the points (1) \leftrightarrow (2) and concurrently between the indices $i \leftrightarrow j$, the list of invariants (5.3), as given by Waławczyk & Oberlack (2016), is not complete: For example, another independent invariant would be $\frac{t_1 t_2}{(t_1 + t_2)^2}$. On the other hand, the proposed invariants a_3 – a_5 in (5.3) are ill-defined when performing the one-point limit $(\mathbf{x}_{(2)}, t_2) \rightarrow (\mathbf{x}_{(1)}, t_1) =: (\mathbf{x}, t)$. A more reasonable choice of invariants would be to take $a_{2+k} = \frac{(x_{(1)k} - x_{(2)k})^2}{t_1 + t_2}$. In particular for HIT only the combined dependence $a_{2+1} + a_{2+2} + a_{2+3}$ is admissible.

[‡]The result of Eq. (34) in Waławczyk & Oberlack (2016) is incorrect in that it misses the complementary term proportional to $1/t_2$. The correct result (5.6) is derived in Appendix B. In order to avoid mistakes when performing the functional derivative (5.6), it is expedient to rename all integration variables in (5.2) and (5.4), e.g. into ‘primed’ variables.

^{‡‡}In Appendix C it is shown that in order to ensure an overall consistent analysis, F_{ij} should not only be constant in the one-point limit $(\mathbf{x}_{(2)}, t_2) \rightarrow (\mathbf{x}_{(1)}, t_1) =: (\mathbf{x}, t)$, but constant globally for all space-time points $(\mathbf{x}_{(1)}, t_1)$ and $(\mathbf{x}_{(2)}, t_2)$. In fact, this will be true for all components of the moment function $\mathbf{F} = (F_{i_1 \dots i_n})$, which means that $\frac{\partial}{\partial t_m} F_{i_1 \dots i_n} = 0$ and $\frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{x}_{(m)}} F_{i_1 \dots i_n} = 0$ for all $n \geq 2$ and $1 \leq m \leq n$.

for $F_{ij} \sim \langle U_i U_j \rangle \neq 0$, does not satisfy the Navier-Stokes-Hopf equation [†]

$$\int \eta_k(\mathbf{x}, t) \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \frac{\delta \Phi}{\delta y_k(\mathbf{x}, t)} - i \frac{\partial}{\partial x_l} \frac{\delta^2 \Phi}{\delta y_k(\mathbf{x}, t) \delta y_l(\mathbf{x}, t)} - \nu \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_l \partial x_l} \frac{\delta \Phi}{\delta y_k(\mathbf{x}, t)} \right] d^3 \mathbf{x} dt = 0, \quad (5.8)$$

which is given by Eq. (14) in Waclawczyk & Oberlack (2016), where the pressure functional Π has been eliminated by the solenoidal (divergence free) testing field $\boldsymbol{\eta}(\mathbf{x}, t)$.[‡] When plugging the consistent solution (5.7) for constant $\mathbf{F} = (F_{i_1 \dots i_n})$ into (5.8), we obtain the relation

$$\int \eta_k(\mathbf{x}, t) \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{F_{kj}}{t} \underbrace{\int y_j(\mathbf{x}', t') d^3 \mathbf{x}' dt'}_{= c_j \text{ (const.)}} + \mathcal{O}(1/t^{3/2}) \right) + 0 \right] d^3 \mathbf{x} dt = 0, \quad (5.9)$$

which can only be satisfied when equating all terms of equal power in t . By equating the lowest order, we then obtain the equation

$$\int \eta_k(\mathbf{x}, t) \left[F_{kj} c_j \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \frac{1}{t} \right] d^3 \mathbf{x} dt = 0, \quad \forall \eta_k, \quad (5.10)$$

which, according to Lewis & Kraichnan (1962), must hold for *all* solenoidal testing fields η_k vanishing sufficiently rapidly at space infinity.^{‡‡} Equation (5.10) can thus only be satisfied, if

$$F_{kj} c_j = 0, \quad \forall c_i, \quad (5.11)$$

which again, since y_i in c_i (5.9) is not specified, must hold for *all* auxiliary functions $y_i \neq 0$ that vanish sufficiently fast at space infinity. Hence, equation (5.11) must hold for *all* finite values of c_i , which thus can only be satisfied, if

$$F_{ij} = 0, \quad \forall i, j. \quad (5.12)$$

This result states that (5.7) is only a solution to the Navier-Stokes-Hopf equation (5.8) if F_{ij} is zero in the limit $(\mathbf{x}_{(2)}, t_2) \rightarrow (\mathbf{x}_{(1)}, t_1)$, which again leads to a zero correlation function [§]

$$\langle U_i(\mathbf{x}_{(1)}, t_1) U_j(\mathbf{x}_{(1)}, t_1) \rangle = 0, \quad (5.13)$$

and not to what is incorrectly and misleadingly claimed after Eq. (34) in Waclawczyk & Oberlack (2016); basically the same mistake they have done in an earlier publication, although we have already pointed out to this in time (see our detailed comment Frewer *et al.* (2016b)).

Just to observe a $1/t$ scaling behavior in some arbitrarily constructed function does not automatically mean that it also qualifies as a physical solution,^{§§} in particular as freely decaying homogeneous isotropic turbulence is more complex than just to analytically ‘solve’ it in the naïve way as proposed in Waclawczyk & Oberlack (2016). This strongly reminds me of the spoof paper published by Beck *et al.* (1931). — With a personal comment of H. A. Bethe (see page link p. 185), the original article and its reaction (p. 186), in ‘calculating’ the absolute zero temperature in Celsius units (not Kelvin!) directly from the dimensionless fine structure constant, was republished in Bethe (1997).

[†]Even if we would symmetrize the solution (5.7), it still would *not* be a consistent solution of the Navier-Stokes-Hopf equation (5.8) for $\langle U_i U_j \rangle \neq 0$; for more details see Appendix D.

[‡]For all details on the derivation of (5.8), see Lewis & Kraichnan (1962) as also cited in Waclawczyk & Oberlack (2016).

^{‡‡}A large class of non-zero, divergence-free functions vanishing at space infinity can be constructed, for example, by the following procedure: $\boldsymbol{\eta} = \nabla \times \boldsymbol{\mu} \neq \mathbf{0}$, with $\boldsymbol{\mu} = (f_1(\mathbf{x}, t) \cdot x_2, 0, -f_2(\mathbf{x}, t) \cdot x_1)$, where the f_i are arbitrary scalar functions in the space-time coordinates with the spatial property $\lim_{\|\mathbf{x}\| \rightarrow \infty} f_i(\mathbf{x}, t) \rightarrow 0$.

[§]This zero result (5.13) is also obtained if we would symmetrize the solution (5.7); see Appendix D.

^{§§}If equipped with a certain sense of physical intuition, one can already see that the correlation function Eq. (34) in the limit $(\mathbf{x}_{(2)}, t_2) \rightarrow (\mathbf{x}_{(1)}, t_1)$ cannot be physically meaningful, because this result is obtained without any restrictions on the bifurcation parameter, the viscosity ν , or equivalently the (initial) Reynolds number Re . In other words, the $1/t$ scaling in the turbulent kinetic energy is universally obtained in Waclawczyk & Oberlack (2016) for *all* Re without any restrictions, which obviously cannot be a reasonable result, since experiments and numerical simulations show that such a scaling can at most only be reached in the limit $Re \rightarrow \infty$.

Appendix A. Combining the “modified” LMN symmetries

The aim of this section is to reproduce the induced transformation (3.3) from the combined “modified” LMN symmetries Eqs. (4) - (6) in Waławczyk & Oberlack (2016) that correctly leaves the proposed function Eq. (9) in Waławczyk & Oberlack (2016), or Eq. (69) in Waławczyk *et al.* (2014), invariant. This combination, as originally introduced and proposed in Waławczyk *et al.* (2014), we start with the scaling group Eq. (4), which will be denoted by the transformation symbol ‘ \sim ’

$$\tilde{\mathbf{x}} = e^{k_2} \mathbf{x}, \quad \tilde{\mathbf{v}} = e^{-k_2} \mathbf{v}, \quad \tilde{f}_1 = e^{3k_2} f_1, \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where it is sufficient to only consider the transformation of the one-point PDF, since the considered transformation (3.3) only concerns the lowest order moment $\langle U \rangle$. First note that the group parameter a_2 in Eq. (4) switched to k_2 after Eq. (6), and then the fact that Eq. (4) contains an essential misprint: The sign in the exponent of the transformed one-point PDF is positive, not negative. Since (A.1) is a dimensional scaling group, this can be readily verified by transforming the dimensionless PDF normalization constraint

$$\int f_1(\mathbf{v}; \mathbf{x}, t) d^3 \mathbf{v} = 1, \quad (\text{A.2})$$

which also after transformation (A.1) should stay dimensionless and unchanged in value, otherwise (A.1) disqualifies to be a symmetry of the LMN equations. It is then combined with the new (unphysical) statistical scaling symmetry Eq. (5), to be denoted by ‘ $\hat{\cdot}$ ’

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}} = \tilde{\mathbf{x}}, \quad \hat{\mathbf{v}} = \tilde{\mathbf{v}}, \quad \hat{f}_1 = \delta^3(\tilde{\mathbf{v}}) + e^{k_2} (\tilde{f}_1 - \delta^3(\tilde{\mathbf{v}})), \quad (\text{A.3})$$

where we put $a_s = k_2$ as in Waławczyk & Oberlack (2016), in order to correspond to the restriction of Eq. (9). Finally, transformation (A.3) is combined with the (unphysical) translation symmetry Eq. (6), which for turbulent channel flow was “modified” to Eq. (54) in Waławczyk *et al.* (2014) as

$$\mathbf{x}^* = \hat{\mathbf{x}}, \quad \mathbf{v}^* = \hat{\mathbf{v}}, \quad f_1^* = \hat{f}_1 + \left(1 - \frac{\hat{x}_2^2}{H^2}\right)^{-1} \cdot \psi \left(\hat{v}_1 \cdot \left(1 - \frac{\hat{x}_2^2}{H^2}\right)^{-1}, \hat{v}_2, \hat{v}_3 \right). \quad (\text{A.4})$$

Now, let’s evaluate the first moment of transformation (A.4):

$$\begin{aligned} \langle U \rangle^* &:= \int f_1^* \cdot v_1^* d^3 \mathbf{v}^* = \int \left[\hat{f}_1 + \left(1 - \frac{\hat{x}_2^2}{H^2}\right)^{-1} \cdot \psi \left(\hat{v}_1 \cdot \left(1 - \frac{\hat{x}_2^2}{H^2}\right)^{-1}, \hat{v}_2, \hat{v}_3 \right) \right] \cdot v_1^* d^3 \mathbf{v}^* \\ &\stackrel{\mathbf{v}^* = \hat{\mathbf{v}}}{=} \int \hat{f}_1 \cdot \hat{v}_1 d^3 \hat{\mathbf{v}} + \underbrace{\left(1 - \frac{\hat{x}_2^2}{H^2}\right)^{-1} \cdot \int \psi(\hat{v}'_1, \hat{v}'_2, \hat{v}'_3) \cdot \hat{v}'_1 d^3 \hat{\mathbf{v}}'}_{\equiv C_1} \\ &\stackrel{\hat{\mathbf{v}} = \tilde{\mathbf{v}}}{=} \int \left(\delta^3(\tilde{\mathbf{v}}) + e^{k_2} (\tilde{f}_1 - \delta^3(\tilde{\mathbf{v}})) \right) \cdot \tilde{v}_1 d^3 \tilde{\mathbf{v}} + C_1 \left(1 - \frac{\hat{x}_2^2}{H^2}\right) \\ &= e^{k_2} \int \tilde{f}_1 \cdot \tilde{v}_1 d^3 \tilde{\mathbf{v}} + C_1 \left(1 - \frac{\hat{x}_2^2}{H^2}\right) \\ &= e^{k_2 + 3k_2 - k_2 - 3k_2} \underbrace{\int f_1 \cdot v_1 d^3 \mathbf{v}}_{= \langle U \rangle} + C_1 \left(1 - \frac{e^{2k_2} x_2^2}{H^2}\right), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.5})$$

which then finally results to the induced moment transformation

$$x_2^* = e^{k_2} x_2, \quad \langle U \rangle^* = \langle U \rangle + C_1 \left(1 - \frac{e^{2k_2} x_2^2}{H^2} \right), \quad (\text{A.6})$$

which, obviously, is not in accord with the transformation (3.3). In particular, this induced transformation (A.6) does not leave *Eq. (9)* invariant as, in contrary, (3.3) does. Important to note here is that the result (A.6) is independent of whether the three transformations (A.1), (A.3) and (A.4) commute or not. Independent of how they are combined, one always gets the unique result (A.6).

Appendix B. Deriving the correct second functional derivative

As noted in Section 5, the second functional derivative *Eq. (34)* in Waclawczyk & Oberlack (2016) has been evaluated incorrectly. Here, the correct expression will be derived.

Taking the second functional derivative of solution *Eq. (27)* with its explicit term *Eq. (33)*, as done in Waclawczyk & Oberlack (2016), we obtain, instead of *Eq. (34)*, the following result:

$$\begin{aligned} \left. \frac{\delta^2 \Phi}{\delta y_i(\mathbf{x}_{(1)}, t_1) \delta y_j(\mathbf{x}_{(2)}, t_2)} \right|_{\mathbf{y}=\mathbf{0}} &= \left. \frac{\delta^2}{\delta y_i(\mathbf{x}_{(1)}, t_1) \delta y_j(\mathbf{x}_{(2)}, t_2)} \right|_{\mathbf{y}=\mathbf{0}} \left(1 + C_1 + C_2 + \dots \right) \\ &= \left. \frac{\delta^2}{\delta y_i(\mathbf{x}_{(1)}, t_1) \delta y_j(\mathbf{x}_{(2)}, t_2)} \right|_{\mathbf{y}=\mathbf{0}} \int \frac{1}{t'_1} F_{kl}(a'_n) y_k(\mathbf{x}'_{(1)}, t'_1) y_l(\mathbf{x}'_{(2)}, t'_2) d^3 \mathbf{x}'_{(1)} dt'_1 d^3 \mathbf{x}'_{(2)} dt'_2 \\ &= \left. \frac{\delta}{\delta y_i(\mathbf{x}_{(1)}, t_1)} \right|_{\mathbf{y}=\mathbf{0}} \int \frac{1}{t'_1} F_{kl}(a'_n) \left\{ y_k(\mathbf{x}'_{(1)}, t'_1) \delta_{jl} \delta^3(\mathbf{x}_{(2)} - \mathbf{x}'_{(2)}) \delta(t_2 - t'_2) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \delta_{jk} \delta^3(\mathbf{x}_{(2)} - \mathbf{x}'_{(1)}) \delta(t_2 - t'_1) y_l(\mathbf{x}'_{(2)}, t'_2) \right\} d^3 \mathbf{x}'_{(1)} dt'_1 d^3 \mathbf{x}'_{(2)} dt'_2 \\ &= \int \frac{1}{t'_1} F_{kl}(a'_n) \left\{ \delta_{ik} \delta^3(\mathbf{x}_{(1)} - \mathbf{x}'_{(1)}) \delta(t_1 - t'_1) \delta_{jl} \delta^3(\mathbf{x}_{(2)} - \mathbf{x}'_{(2)}) \delta(t_2 - t'_2) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \delta_{jk} \delta^3(\mathbf{x}_{(2)} - \mathbf{x}'_{(1)}) \delta(t_2 - t'_1) \delta_{il} \delta^3(\mathbf{x}_{(1)} - \mathbf{x}'_{(2)}) \delta(t_1 - t'_2) \right\} d^3 \mathbf{x}'_{(1)} dt'_1 d^3 \mathbf{x}'_{(2)} dt'_2 \\ &= \frac{1}{t_1} F_{ij}(a_n) + \frac{1}{t_2} F_{ji}(b_n), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.1})$$

where the arguments b_n are connected to the a_n (5.3) as (see also first footnote on p. 6)

$$b_1 = \frac{1}{a_1}, \quad b_2 = -a_1 a_2, \quad b_{2+k} = -a_{2+k}, \quad k = 1, 2, 3. \quad (\text{B.2})$$

Appendix C. The constancy of \mathbf{F} as result of a consistent analysis

This section proves that in order to guarantee an overall consistent analysis up to all orders for homogeneous isotropic turbulence (HIT), the corresponding scale-invariant moment functions $\mathbf{F} = (F_{i_1 \dots i_n})$ defining the functional expansion (5.1)

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi &= 1 + \underbrace{C_1}_{=0} + C_2 + C_3 + \dots = 1 + \underbrace{\int \frac{1}{t_1^{1/2}} F_{i'}(1') y_{i'}(1') d1'}_{=0} + \int \frac{1}{t_1^{2/2}} F_{i'j'}(1', 2') y_{i'}(1') y_{j'}(2') d1' d2' \\ &\quad + \int \frac{1}{t_1^{3/2}} F_{i'j'k'}(1', 2', 3') y_{i'}(1') y_{j'}(2') y_{k'}(3') d1' d2' d3' + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.1})$$

has to be for all orders globally constant in space and time, where the general space-time multi-point $(\mathbf{x}'_{(n)}, t'_n)$ in (C.1) has been abbreviated for convenience to (n') . The starting point of the proof is to recognize that the multi-point velocity correlations are connected to the functions $F_{i_1 \dots i_n}$ in the following general way (shown here only for the second and third order)

$$\left. \begin{aligned} i^2 \langle U_i(1) U_j(2) \rangle &= \frac{\delta^2 \Phi}{\delta y_i(1) \delta y_j(2)} \Big|_{\mathbf{y}=\mathbf{0}} = \frac{1}{t_1} F_{ij}(1, 2) + \frac{1}{t_2} F_{ji}(2, 1), \\ i^3 \langle U_i(1) U_j(2) U_k(3) \rangle &= \frac{\delta^3 \Phi}{\delta y_i(1) \delta y_j(2) \delta y_k(3)} \Big|_{\mathbf{y}=\mathbf{0}} = \frac{1}{t_1^{3/2}} F_{ijk}(1, 2, 3) + \frac{1}{t_1^{3/2}} F_{ikj}(1, 3, 2) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{t_2^{3/2}} F_{jik}(2, 1, 3) + \frac{1}{t_2^{3/2}} F_{jki}(2, 3, 1) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{t_3^{3/2}} F_{kij}(3, 1, 2) + \frac{1}{t_3^{3/2}} F_{kji}(3, 2, 1). \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (\text{C.2})$$

Now, to evaluate the Navier-Stokes-Hopf equation (5.8) we first need to evaluate the two functional derivatives, which for the specific solution ansatz (C.1) reads

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \frac{\delta \Phi}{\delta y_k(0)} &= \int \frac{1}{t} F_{kj'}(0, 2') y_{j'}(2') d2' + \int \frac{1}{t_1} F_{i'k}(1', 0) y_{i'}(1') d1' \\ &\quad + \int \frac{1}{t^{3/2}} F_{kj'k'}(0, 2', 3') y_{j'}(2') y_{k'}(3') d2' d3' \\ &\quad + \int \frac{1}{t_1^{3/2}} F_{i'kk'}(1', 0, 3') y_{i'}(1') y_{k'}(3') d1' d3' \\ &\quad + \int \frac{1}{t_1^{3/2}} F_{i'j'k}(1', 2', 0) y_{i'}(1') y_{j'}(2') d1' d2' \\ &\quad + \mathcal{O}(y_{n'}^3), \\ \frac{\delta^2 \Phi}{\delta y_k(0) \delta y_l(0)} &= \frac{1}{t} F_{kl}(0, 0) + \frac{1}{t} F_{lk}(0, 0) \\ &\quad + \int \frac{1}{t^{3/2}} F_{klk'}(0, 0, 3') y_{k'}(3') d3' + \int \frac{1}{t^{3/2}} F_{lkk'}(0, 0, 3') y_{k'}(3') d3' \\ &\quad + \int \frac{1}{t^{3/2}} F_{kj'l}(0, 2', 0) y_{j'}(2') d2' + \int \frac{1}{t^{3/2}} F_{lj'k}(0, 2', 0) y_{j'}(2') d2' \\ &\quad + \int \frac{1}{t_1^{3/2}} F_{i'kl}(1', 0, 0) y_{i'}(1') d1' + \int \frac{1}{t_1^{3/2}} F_{i'lk}(1', 0, 0) y_{i'}(1') d1' \\ &\quad + \mathcal{O}(y_{n'}^2), \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (\text{C.3})$$

where the 0 abbreviates the arbitrary space-time point (\mathbf{x}, t) . Since the solution ansatz (C.1) constitutes a polynomial expansion in the auxiliary variable y_n , the Navier-Stokes-Hopf equation (5.8) can only be satisfied when equating equal orders in y_n , since the solution (C.1) should be valid for *all* functions y_n that vanish sufficiently fast at space infinity. Furthermore, since the Navier-Stokes-Hopf equation (5.8) itself should also hold for all solenoidal testing fields η_k vanishing sufficiently fast at space infinity, too, the zeroth-order in y_n thus then equates to

$$-i \frac{\partial}{\partial x_l} \left(\frac{1}{t} F_{kl}(0, 0) + \frac{1}{t} F_{lk}(0, 0) \right) = 0, \quad (\text{C.4})$$

and the first (linear) order in y_n to (after renaming the summation indices and integration variables appropriately)

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{1}{t} F_{ki}(0, 1) + \frac{1}{t_1} F_{ik}(1, 0) \right) - \nu \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_l \partial x_l} \left(\frac{1}{t} F_{ki}(0, 1) + \frac{1}{t_1} F_{ik}(1, 0) \right) \\ & - i \frac{\partial}{\partial x_l} \left(\frac{1}{t^{3/2}} F_{kli}(0, 0, 1) + \frac{1}{t^{3/2}} F_{lki}(0, 0, 1) \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \frac{1}{t^{3/2}} F_{kil}(0, 1, 0) + \frac{1}{t^{3/2}} F_{lik}(0, 1, 0) + \frac{1}{t_1^{3/2}} F_{ikl}(1, 0, 0) + \frac{1}{t_1^{3/2}} F_{ilk}(1, 0, 0) \right) = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.5})$$

The aim now is to find at least one particular solution for F_{ij} and F_{ijk} that satisfy the determining equations (C.4) and (C.5). The standard problem hereby again is that this system itself is unclosed, exactly as it is the case for the velocity correlations: To determine the third-order moment functions F_{ijk} , the next higher order in y_n is needed and so on, thus eventually inducing an infinite chain of equations.

A closer inspection, however, reveals that this infinite chain is not needed, simply because it is already inconsistent at its lowest level. While the zeroth-order equation (C.4) is identically satisfied under the 1-point restriction of Waclawczyk & Oberlack (2016), namely that $F_{kl}(0, 0)$ is to be a constant (see their argument on *p.* 7), it is the linear-order equation (C.5) that is inconsistent for the flow configuration (HIT) considered herein. This can be readily seen by rewriting (C.5) in terms of the velocity correlations using the relations of (C.2)

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \langle U_k(0) U_i(1) \rangle + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_l} \langle U_k(0) U_l(0) U_i(1) \rangle - \nu \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_l \partial x_l} \langle U_k(0) U_i(1) \rangle = 0, \quad (\text{C.6})$$

and recognizing that the 2-point velocity correlation equation for HIT is actually given by[†]

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \langle U_k(0) U_i(1) \rangle + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_l} \langle U_k(0) U_l(0) U_i(1) \rangle + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_{(1)l}} \langle U_k(0) U_l(1) U_i(1) \rangle \\ & - \nu \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_l \partial x_l} \langle U_k(0) U_i(1) \rangle - \nu \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_{(1)l} \partial x_{(1)l}} \langle U_k(0) U_i(1) \rangle = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.7})$$

thus showing that the following consistency relations have to hold

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_{(1)l}} \langle U_k(0) U_l(1) U_i(1) \rangle = 0, \quad \nu \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_{(1)l} \partial x_{(1)l}} \langle U_k(0) U_i(1) \rangle = 0, \quad (\text{C.8})$$

so that (C.7) will match with (C.6).[‡] But now, if (C.8) holds, then the following relations should hold too

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_l} \langle U_k(0) U_l(0) U_i(1) \rangle = 0, \quad \nu \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_l \partial x_l} \langle U_k(0) U_i(1) \rangle = 0, \quad (\text{C.9})$$

[†]Note that for HIT the pressure-velocity correlations in the 2-point velocity correlation equation are zero and thus not contributing.

[‡]It may seem that the missing terms in (C.6) is due to that the solution ansatz (C.1) is not symmetrized relative to the time coordinate. But this is not the case as the next section shows, because when making the fully symmetrized ansatz (D.1)-(D.2), it simply can be reduced back again to the non-symmetrized ansatz (C.1) by just renaming the summation indices and integration variables appropriately. The resulting coefficient functions of each order n can then be added up to the single function $F_{i_1 \dots i_n} := \sum_{\alpha=1}^n F_{\{i_1 \dots i_n\}}^{(\alpha)}$ to effectively yield the same overall result, as can be explicitly seen when comparing, for example, the second order results in (D.3) and (C.2), where both representations give the same result for the 2-point velocity correlation, irrespective of whether the solution ansatz for Φ is symmetrized in t_n or not.

where again, as in Section 5 along with the proof in Appendix C, we consider the consistent HIT solution $F_{ij}^{(n)} = \text{const.}$, assuming that $F_{ij}^{(1)} \neq F_{ij}^{(2)}$ in order to keep the most general outline put forward here. Solution (D.1) then reduces to the symmetrized version of (5.7)

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi = & 1 + F_{ij}^{(1)} \cdot \int \frac{1}{t_1} y_i(\mathbf{x}_{(1)}, t_1) y_j(\mathbf{x}_{(2)}, t_2) d^3 \mathbf{x}_{(1)} dt_1 d^3 \mathbf{x}_{(2)} dt_2 \\ & + F_{ij}^{(2)} \cdot \int \frac{1}{t_2} y_i(\mathbf{x}_{(1)}, t_1) y_j(\mathbf{x}_{(2)}, t_2) d^3 \mathbf{x}_{(1)} dt_1 d^3 \mathbf{x}_{(2)} dt_2 + \mathcal{O}(1/t_n^{3/2}). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{D.4})$$

When plugging this solution into the Navier-Stokes-Hopf equation (5.8), we obtain the symmetrized version of relation (5.9)

$$\int \eta_k(\mathbf{x}, t) \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{F_{kj}^{(1)} c_j}{t} + \frac{F_{ik}^{(2)} c_i}{t} + \mathcal{O}(1/t^{3/2}) \right) + 0 \right] d^3 \mathbf{x} dt = 0, \quad (\text{D.5})$$

which, as explained in Section 5, can only be satisfied if each order in t is equated separately, i.e., for the lowest order if

$$\left(F_{ki}^{(1)} + F_{ik}^{(2)} \right) c_i = 0, \quad \forall c_i, \quad (\text{D.6})$$

which again, as explained in Section 5, can be satisfied for all finite values c_i only if

$$F_{ij}^{(2)} = -F_{ji}^{(1)}. \quad (\text{D.7})$$

Hence, in the considered limit $(\mathbf{x}_{(2)}, t_2) \rightarrow (\mathbf{x}_{(1)}, t_1)$, the second moment relation (D.3) thus reduces to

$$i^2 \langle U_i(\mathbf{x}_{(1)}, t_1) U_j(\mathbf{x}_{(1)}, t_1) \rangle = \frac{1}{t_1} \left(F_{ij}^{(1)} - F_{ij}^{(1)} \right) + \frac{1}{t_1} \left(-F_{ji}^{(1)} + F_{ji}^{(1)} \right), \quad (\text{D.8})$$

which then directly evaluates to zero:

$$\langle U_i(\mathbf{x}_{(1)}, t_1) U_j(\mathbf{x}_{(1)}, t_1) \rangle = 0. \quad (\text{D.9})$$

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